

Simulating Waves with TIO and DFB Methods

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Abstract

The present work applies the Dimensionless Fluctuation Balance (DFB) framework to wave propagation and combines it with the Time Invariance Operator (TIO) to investigate heterogeneous domains. Starting from a dimensionless balance between spatial and temporal phase variations, the classical wave equation is recovered through a phase-coherence argument. The equation is then rewritten as a first-order dynamical system using the Method of Lines, allowing the wave height and its temporal derivative to be treated as components of a local state vector. The TIO operator is applied over the discrete spatial term, introducing localized invariant regions into the propagation medium. Numerical simulations show that these regions modify the wave dynamics, producing reflections, scattering, interference, and wavefront deformation. The results indicate that DFB provides a direct route to the wave equation, while TIO offers a simple mechanism for representing barriers, inclusions, and heterogeneous structures in wave propagation problems.

Keywords: PDEs, Dimensionless Fluctuation Balance, Time Invariance Operator

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1 Introduction

Wave propagation is one of the fundamental phenomena described by partial differential equations in mathematical physics. The classical wave equation appears in several contexts, including mechanical waves, acoustic systems, electromagnetic fields, elastic media, and fluid surfaces. In its usual formulation, this equation is obtained from mechanical balance laws, constitutive assumptions, or variational principles. Although these routes are well established, alternative formulations based on fluctuation relations may provide additional insight into the origin of propagation dynamics.

The Dimensionless Fluctuation Balance (DFB) framework was recently introduced as a methodology capable of obtaining physical relations from dimensionless balance conditions. Rather than beginning from conservation laws in their conventional form, DFB starts from relative variations between interacting physical quantities and derives governing equations from compatibility conditions. In the context of wave propagation, the relevant balance is associated with the preservation of phase coherence. A wave pulse can preserve its form during propagation only when the spatial and temporal contributions to the phase remain compatible.

In parallel, the Time Invariance Operator (TIO) was proposed as a mechanism capable of introducing localized modifications into differential equations while preserving the global

numerical structure of the original model. Previous applications demonstrated its ability to modify wave propagation, diffraction, and interference patterns through spatially localized operators. This makes TIO a useful tool for representing barriers, inclusions, obstacles, and heterogeneous regions in wave propagation problems.

The purpose of the present work is to combine these two approaches. First, the wave equation is obtained from a DFB formulation based on the balance between spatial and temporal phase fluctuations. Second, the resulting equation is rewritten as a first-order dynamical system using the Method of Lines, allowing the wave height and its temporal derivative to be treated as components of a local state vector. Finally, the TIO operator is applied over the discrete spatial operator in a two-dimensional domain.

Numerical simulations are then performed to investigate how localized invariant regions affect wave propagation in a closed heterogeneous domain. The results show that the TIO structures remain embedded in the medium and modify the wave dynamics by producing reflections, scattering, interference, and local wavefront deformation. These findings suggest that DFB and TIO can be combined into a compact framework for deriving and simulating wave equations in heterogeneous systems.

2 DFB and TIO Applied to Waves

2.1 Dimensionless Fluctuations Balance of Wave Equation

A change in the state of a wave field in a closed region, containing a wave height u , starts when a localized disturbance is established inside the domain. The disturbance propagates through the reference region while preserving the coherence between the spatial and temporal contributions of the wave phase. In order to preserve its shape while traveling, a wave pulse must keep the spatial phase variation $k\delta x$ balanced with the temporal phase variation $\omega\delta t$. Otherwise, different parts of the pulse would evolve with incompatible space-time rates, producing deformation or loss of coherence. Since the spatial phase is represented by kx and the temporal phase by ωt . Then, the dimensionless fluctuation balance for wave propagation can be written as,

$$\frac{\delta(kx)}{kx} = \pm \frac{\delta(\omega t)}{\omega t}. \quad (1)$$

Following the same balance-based approach presented in [1], the objective here is to obtain a wave propagation equation. In the present case, the balance is associated with the preservation of phase coherence during propagation. The quantities kx and ωt represent the spatial and temporal contributions to the wave phase, respectively. Therefore, when the phase balance is imposed, a spatial fluctuation must be accompanied by a compatible temporal fluctuation, leading to

$$\delta x = \pm \frac{kx \omega}{\omega t k} \delta t. \quad (2)$$

This relation indicates that the pulse propagates with a characteristic velocity determined by the compatibility between the spatial and temporal phase variations. Along a coherent propagation path, the ratio between spatial displacement and elapsed time is identified

with the phase velocity of the wave. Since the wave profile must preserve its form during propagation, the evolution of the wave height u can be written as a first-order propagation equation for $u(x, t)$, given by

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \pm c \frac{\partial u}{\partial x}. \quad (3)$$

Considering the two possible propagation directions, the first-order directional operators can be combined through D'Alembert's factorization. This composition leads to the second-order propagation equation for $u(x, t)$,

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + c \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - c \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right) u = 0, \quad (4)$$

which gives the classical one-dimensional wave equation,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}. \quad (5)$$

In higher dimensions, the spatial second derivative is naturally generalized by the Laplacian operator. Thus, the wave equation can be written as,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = c^2 \nabla^2 u. \quad (6)$$

Next, the TIO operator is applied to equation (6), enabling wave simulations over heterogeneous regions.

2.2 Time Invariance Operator in Wave Equation

The temporal evolution of the wave equation over a two-dimensional matrix domain is treated using the Method of Lines. In this approach, only the spatial variables are discretized, while the temporal evolution remains continuous. As a consequence, the second-order wave equation is rewritten as a first-order dynamical system in time, which can be integrated by standard ODE solvers. The indices i and j identify positions inside the two-dimensional matrix domain. Thus, the temporal derivative of the wave height is used to define an auxiliary variable $v_{i,j}$, allowing the local state vector $\psi_{i,j}$, as follows

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} \longrightarrow \psi_{i,j} = \begin{bmatrix} u_{i,j} \\ v_{i,j} \end{bmatrix}, \quad v_{i,j} = \frac{du_{i,j}}{dt}. \quad (7)$$

In equation (7), the temporal evolution is rewritten in terms of the local state vector $\psi_{i,j}$. This representation separates the wave height $u_{i,j}$ and its temporal derivative $v_{i,j}$ into two components of the same dynamical system. After this reduction of order, the spatial contribution of the wave equation can be represented over the same two-dimensional matrix domain. The term $S_{i,j}$ denotes the discrete spatial operator applied to each matrix position,

$$\nabla^2 u = S_{i,j}. \quad (8)$$

Replacing the temporal evolution in the wave equation and applying the TIO operator over the spatial term, it is possible to obtain the final form shown in equation (9). This form

is similar to equation (9) presented in [2], where the left-hand side contains the temporal evolution and the right-hand side contains the TIO operator acting through a Hadamard product over the spatial discretization.

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} \longrightarrow \frac{d\psi_{i,j}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} u_{i,j} \\ v_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{i,j} \\ c^2 T_{i,j} \circ S_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Here, $T_{i,j}$ denotes the TIO matrix defined over the discrete domain, and \circ represents the Hadamard product applied pointwise over the spatial operator matrix. Since the state vector $\psi_{i,j}$ contains both $u_{i,j}$ and their derivative $v_{i,j}$, equation (9) represents the first-order system integrated in time by the ODE solver. Therefore, this formulation is equivalent to solving the original second-order wave equation, with the TIO operator acting directly over the discrete spatial contribution. After the discretization procedure over the two-dimensional domain, numerical simulations can be directly implemented. The matrices generated at each selected time state may be interpreted as numerical maps of the wave-height field, which can be converted into images to visualize the propagation pattern. In this way, the temporal evolution of the wave can be analyzed through successive snapshots of the field $u(x, y, t)$.

The simulations were performed using the Method of Lines [3] and [5], following the numerical treatment of partial differential equations in which only the spatial variables are discretized. The computational domain consisted of a uniform 100 by 100 grid, where the spatial discretization transformed the wave equation into a system of ordinary differential equations. Time integration was carried out using the adaptive ODE45 solver implemented in GNU Octave [4]. This numerical framework was employed to investigate wave propagation in closed heterogeneous domains containing localized heterogeneities introduced by the Time Invariance Operator. Initially, the wave field evolves from a localized vertical disturbance. As propagation advances, the closed boundaries impose reflections, while the localized structures introduced through the Time Invariance Operator modify the wave transport inside the domain. These invariant regions act as fixed spatial constraints in the propagation medium, producing scattering, interference, and local modifications of the wavefront. The persistence of these structures throughout the simulation indicates that the TIO operator can be employed to represent localized barriers, inclusions, or heterogeneous regions in wave propagation problems.

3 Waves Simulation with Heterogeneous Domain

Figure 1: Wave equation simulation in a closed heterogeneous domain. A localized vertical disturbance was used as the initial condition. Sixteen equally spaced time states were sampled during the simulation. Four invariant regions introduced by the TIO operator can be observed through the evolution of the wavefront.

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5 Concluding Remarks

In this work, the wave equation was obtained from the Dimensionless Fluctuation Balance method by imposing a balance between the spatial and temporal contributions of the wave phase. Starting from this phase-coherence condition, a first-order propagation relation was derived and then combined through D'Alembert's factorization, recovering the classical second-order wave equation. The formulation was extended to two-dimensional domains by introducing the Laplacian operator and was rewritten as a first-order dynamical system using the Method of Lines. The discrete system was combined with the Time Invariance Operator, allowing localized invariant regions to be introduced directly over the spatial operator. The numerical simulations showed that these regions remain embedded in the propagation medium and modify the wave dynamics throughout the temporal evolution. The generated patterns reveal reflections, scattering, interference, and local wavefront deformation caused by the interaction between the propagating field, the closed boundaries, and the TIO-defined structures. These results indicate that DFB provides a direct route for obtaining the wave equation from a dimensionless phase-balance argument, while TIO offers a simple mechanism for representing localized barriers, inclusions, obstacles, or heterogeneous regions in wave propagation problems. More broadly, the combination of DFB-derived equations with TIO-based spatial modifications provides a compact framework that may be extended to other wave systems and heterogeneous media.

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